

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS IN EGG PRODUCTION

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Abstract

The effect of the combined use of two forms of benzoic acid and mannanoligosaccharides on egg production and egg weight in chickens was studied. The effect of using the Sal-Zap organic acid complex at various dosages on quail egg weight was also studied. The results allowed us to determine the optimal dosages. A combination of 750 g of concentrated benzoic acid, 200 g/t of coated benzoic acid, and 400 g of Actigen per 1 ton of laying hens' feed demonstrated the most consistent results. A Sal-Zap dosage of 750 g/t in quail feed was determined to be the best. These levels can be recommended for nutritionists specializing in laying hens and quails.

Keywords: antibiotics, benzoic acid, coated benzoic acid, mannanoligosaccharides, Actigen, Sal-Zap, laying hens, laying rate.

In a number of countries, the use of antibiotics in poultry feed is prohibited by law unless it is used to treat diseases. Consequently, research into antibiotic substitutes has intensified. Promising alternatives include plant components and their derivatives, probiotics, prebiotics, and organic acids [1]. Organic acids have proven effective in optimizing gastrointestinal function. Scientific experiments have confirmed their positive impact on intestinal development and health in laying hens and male pigs [7]. The key advantage of organic acids as an alternative to antibiotics is their ability to act directly in feed by lowering pH [3]. This has a dual effect:

- improves nutrient absorption;
- suppresses pathogenic microorganisms both in feed and in the animal's digestive system [8].

Benzoic acid belongs to a group of simple aromatic carboxylic acids. Benzoic acid in broiler feed affects live weight gain and improves feed conversion. However, high doses of benzoic acid can negatively impact bird health and performance. Protected benzoic acid, which appears as white granules, unlike its concentrated, unprotected form, dissociates primarily in the lower intestine, maintaining a low pH in the duodenum and jejunum favorable for the beneficial microflora found in the small intestine [6].

Mannan oligosaccharides, derived from the outer walls of yeast cells, have a positive effect on the structure of intestinal villi and, as a result, on poultry performance. Over the past two decades, the problem of antibiotic resistance in pathogenic bacteria has prompted research and practice worldwide to develop numerous solutions to achieve production results without the use of feed antibiotics. One such product is Bio-Mos [9], and the next version of this product is Actigen – mannan-enriched fractions extracted from the Bio-Mos structure.

The complex acidifier Sal-Zap, a mixture of propionic, acetic, and sorbic acids, effectively combats pathogenic microflora entering the poultry body from outside. In the feed industry, animal proteins, particularly fishmeal, are one of the main sources of Salmonella. Sal-Zap has proven itself to be an effective inhibitor of pathogenic microflora growth during fishmeal production [2].

The literature we reviewed confirms the positive role of various feed additives that modulate the microbiota and villus structure of poultry intestines in increasing poultry productivity. However, the scientific literature lacks data emphasizing the comprehensive study of organic acids and mannanoligosaccharides in terms of their impact on egg production in laying hens, which underscores the novelty and relevance of our study.

The objective of the study was to evaluate the effect of organic acids and mannanoligosaccharides in compound feed for laying hens and quail on egg production.

To achieve this goal, the following **tasks** were set:

- To study the synergistic effect of benzoic acid in different forms, concentrated and coated, on egg production in laying hens;
- To study the possibility of achieving an enhancing effect by adding mannanoligosaccharides in combination with benzoic acid;
- To determine the effect of different doses of Sal-Zap on egg production in laying quail;
- To study the effect of the factors studied on egg weight.

Materials and Methods. Nine-month studies on laying hens were conducted in the experimental poultry house of the Bashkir State Agrarian University, Ufa, Republic of Bashkortostan, Russia, from early January

to late September 2025. Quail experiments were conducted from mid-March to late August 2025 at a quail farm in the Republic of Bashkortostan, Russia. The experiment lasted six months.

For the first experiment, four groups of SuperNik laying hens were randomly selected, each containing 42 birds. The birds were 245 days old at the beginning of the experiment. The second experiment was conducted on Manchurian quails. Fifty 46-day-old quail were selected.

The first experiment involved studying the productivity of laying hens using feed additives in the following combinations: 750 g of concentrated benzoic acid per ton of feed + 200 g/t coated benzoic acid were added to the diet of birds in a Treatment 1, while Treatment 2 group received 750 g of concentrated benzoic acid + 200 g/t coated benzoic acid + 400 g/t mannanoligosaccharides as Actigen. In the experiment on quail, different doses of the acidifier Sal-Zap were studied: Treatment 1 group received Sal-Zap in the amount of 500 g/t of feed, Treatment 2 group – 750 g/t, and Treatment 3 group – 1000 g/t.

Eggs were collected manually, recording daily collection from each group and maintaining a separate record of the number of eggs with cracks. The resulting digital data was processed using variation statistics using Microsoft Office Excel. The significance and magnitude of differences were assessed using Student's t-tests.

The study revealed a positive effect of using a combination of two forms of benzoic acid and the addition of mannanoligosaccharides on the egg production of laying hens (Figure 1). Birds in the Treatment 1, which received a mixture of protected and concentrated benzoic acid, showed a cumulative increase of 3.17% by the end of the experiment compared to the control group. Treatment 2 group outperformed the control group by 3.92%. Thus, we see that the addition of Actigen contributed to an additional productivity of 0.75% compared to the Treatment 1, which in absolute terms increased the gross harvest by 154 eggs (and +613 eggs vs. Control).

Figure 1. Cumulative egg production of laying hens, %

We noted a similar trend in the number of eggs with cracks: the largest proportion of cracks in the total egg collection was recorded in the control group, while

Treatment 1 and Treatment 2 improved this indicator by 0.22% and 0.31%, respectively (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Crack, % of gross egg yield of laying hens

In Figure 3, we see that the weight of eggs obtained from the experimental groups consuming feed supplemented with benzoic acid and Actigen significantly differed from the control by 2.79% or 1.65 g and 4.09% or 2.42 g, respectively ($p \leq 0.001$). In our opinion, the increase in egg weight is explained by improved digestion and absorption of feed nutrients as a

result of the positive effect of the studied products on the condition of the intestinal villi, which is consistent with literature data describing the modification of intestinal morphology and optimization of the microbiome when using benzoic acid and mannanoligosaccharides in poultry diets [4, 5].

$c - p \leq 0.001$

Figure 3. Weight of laying hens' eggs, g

A quail experiment also showed positive changes in egg weight when using Sal-Zap as a feed acidifier. Adding 750 g/t of the product (Treatment 2) yielded

better results, increasing egg weight by 0.48 g or 3.60% ($p \leq 0.05$).

$a - p \leq 0.05$

Figure 4. Weight of quail eggs, g

Treatments have shown that acidifying compound feed for laying hens and quails has a positive effect on egg production and egg weight. The results highlight improved nutrient absorption due to modification of the intestinal microflora by lowering the pH. These findings have practical significance for producers of chicken and quail eggs.

Conclusion. Studies of various feed acidifiers and mannanoligosaccharides at various dosages revealed positive trends in improving production indicators. Using a combination of biologically active additives in laying hens' feed: concentrated benzoic acid at 750 g/t of feed, coated benzoic acid at 200 g/t, and mannanoligosaccharides at 400 g/t yields the best results. In quail

feed, the complex preparation Sal-Zap is most appropriately used at a dosage of 750 g/t of feed.

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